

Analysis on Implementation of Non-Smoking Area (KTR) Policy in STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan

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ABSTRACT

The percentage of residents of Padangsidimpuan City aged ≥ 10 years in 2017 who smoked every day at 26.8% was in the 5th position highest by Regency/City in Sumatera Utara Province. One effort to reduce exposure to cigarette smoke, the Padangsidimpuan City Government issued a local regulation No. 7 of 2012 concerning non-smoking area (KTR). The KTR compliance survey report in Padangsidimpuan City in 2017 shows that the place of teaching and learning process is the second lowest place of 7% of the 7 settings in establishing and implementing KTR. This research is a development research that aims to (1)make STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan a pilot education institution that applies KTR regional regulation policies in Padangsidimpuan City, (2)new forms and types of models based on KTR regional regulation policies at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan, (3)develop KTR regional regulation policy as a promotional media for the people of Padangsidimpuan City and preventive measures to prevent smoking-related diseases. Informants in this study were the Chair of STIKES, Chair of Facilities/Infrastructure, Chair of Student Affairs for Lecturers, Employees, Security Guardians, Students, Student Parents and Seller of the Cafeteria. Data collected by interview, observation, documentation. Data were analyzed with the Miles and Huberman Models. Qualitative data capture in year I, namely (1)the existence of a written policy on KTR, (2)the presence of personnel assigned to monitor KTR, (3)the existence of promotional media about the smoking ban/KTR. Year II (1)KTR implementation socialization was carried out either directly (face to face) or indirectly (through print, electronic media), (2)there was a

set of tasks and responsibilities in the implementation of KTR (3)attachment of KTR policy announcements through posters, signs smoking bans, bulletin boards, circulars, loudspeakers, (4)KTR signs installed, (5)implementation of KTR counseling and the dangers of smoking and smoking ethics. Year III (1)non-smoking environments, (2)non-smokers reprimand those who smoke in the KTR environment, (3)smokers smoke outside the KTR, (4)there are sanctions for those who violate KTR. The application of KTR regional regulation policy in STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan is based on health promotion which has several prospects to increase its benefits for the community in relation to developing quality and quantity in a developing region, especially educational institutions in Padangsidimpuan City as an education city. The implementation of the KTR regional regulation policy is expected to be able to anticipate and form a form of research synergy, centers in Padangsidimpuan City, Padangsidimpuan City government and the community.

Keywords: Non-Smoking Area (KTR), STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan, Padangsidimpuan City

INTRODUCTION

Smoking behavior is still a global health problem because it can cause various diseases and even death. Smoking is very dangerous and damages the health of both active smokers and those around the smoker (passive smokers) because cigarettes contain substances that are very harmful to health.

Smoking has become so widespread in the world. There are 1.26 billion smokers

worldwide. WHO predicts that diseases related to smoking will become health problems in the world. The number of smokers of women is higher exposed to cigarette smoke by 40.5% than men by 24.2%, even in children aged 0-14 years who are exposed to cigarette smoke by 57.3% or equivalent to 40.3 million children exposed cigarette smoke in the house and in public places. For every 10 adults who died, 1 of them died because of cigarette smoke. The latest WHO data in 2014 was found to have reached 5 million deaths due to cigarettes, while more than 600 thousand people died due to exposure to cigarette smoke. The cause of death from smoking occurs annually in several developing countries (70%), including in Asia and Indonesia. The most common cause of death is chronic lung disease, stroke, tuberculosis, hypertension, diabetes, heart disease, and cancer. It is estimated that by 2030 deaths due to smoking will reach 10 million per year and in developing countries it is estimated that no less than 70% of deaths including Indonesia (WHO, 2015).

The Asean Tobacco Control Atlas in 2014 states that the world population consumes 57% of tobacco, namely the population of Asia and Australia, 14% of the population of Eastern Europe and the Soviet Union, 12% of the American population, 9% of the population of western Europe and 8% of the population of the East Central as well as Africa. The highest percentage of smokers in the population in ASEAN countries are Indonesia (46.16%), the Philippines (16.62%), Vietnam (14.11%), Myanmar (8.73%), Thailand (7.74%), Malaysia (2.90%), Laos (1.23%), Singapore (0.39%), and Brunei (0.04%), thus Indonesia ranks first in smokers in the ASEAN region (Lian, Tan Yen and Dorotheo, Ulysses, 2014).

Indonesia's position in the last five years among the countries with the highest number of smokers in the world has shifted from the 5th country to the highest number of smokers in the world, namely China (38%), the United States (5%), Japan (4%),

and Indonesia (4%) is the third country after China and India, with 65 million smokers or 28% per population, estimated at 225 billion cigarettes smoked per year. In 2014 Indonesia consumed 360 billion cigarettes. Based on the proportion of cigarettes recorded 300 million cigarettes were produced in 2011 and increased in 2013 to 270 billion sticks. Indonesia was the sixth largest tobacco producing country in the world in 2014 (IISD, 2015).

According to a recent study from the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) in 2012 a global research organization at the University of Washington, based on gender the number or proportion of male smokers in Indonesia increased and ranked second in the world with 57% under Timor Leste 61%. The 2014 Global Youth Tobacco Survey (GYTS) stated that Indonesia is the country with the highest number of child smokers in the world. The age of first attempt to smoke by age group and gender according to GYTS in 2014, where most men first smoked age -13-17 years by 88.3%. The total number of first boys surveyed was found to be 19.4% tobacco smoke, 18.3% cigarette smoke and 2.1% electric cigarette smoke over the past 30 days. A total of 54.1% of the men surveyed had smoked even though there were only 1-2 puffs. The proportion of the average number of cigarettes consumed by sex most of the men smoked 1 cigarette per day as much as 35.6% (Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia, 2013).

According to Riskesdas in 2013, more than 30% of Indonesians who smoke reportedly started consuming cigarettes before reaching the age of 10 years. Even more tragically, Indonesia ranks 1st out of 10 ASEAN countries. The number of age trends starting to smoke for men aged 4-14 years reaches 19.6% of the entire population of Indonesia. The number of smokers in Indonesia with age ≥ 10 years has increased, in 2010 amounted to 34.7% and in 2013 increased to 36.3%. The average number of cigarettes smoked per day of the population

aged ≥ 10 years in Indonesia is 12.3 sticks (equivalent to one pack). The average number of cigarettes smoked was found in Bangka Belitung Province (18 cigarettes).

Sumatera Utara Province is one of the provinces that has the highest number of smokers in Indonesia, ranking 12th out of 33 provinces in Indonesia with a percentage of 24.2% smokers, sometimes 4.2%, ex-smokers as much as 3.3% and non-smokers as much as 68.2%. The average number of cigarettes smoked by population aged ≥ 10 years was 14.9 cigarettes (Risksedas, 2013).

The acceleration of the implementation of the Healthy Indonesia Program with the Family Approach (PIS-PK) is one of the activities programs of the Sumatera Utara Provincial Health Office. The program is carried out with the background for the sake of increasing the degree of public health. This program is organized through a family approach. Through the integration of Individual Health Efforts (UKP) and Community Health Efforts (UKM) on an ongoing basis the data and information from the family health profile. 12 (twelve) main indicators are established as markers of a family's health status, including the coverage of non-smoking family members. Coverage of no family members who smoked in Padangsidimpuan City in 2017 was 23.6% (stated that the high number of smokers in Padangsidimpuan City) (Health Office of Sumatera Utara, 2017).

The percentage of population in the City of Padangsidimpuan aged ≥ 10 years who smoked every day at 26.8% was in the fifth position according to regencies/cities in Sumatera Utara Province. The average number of cigarettes smoked per day of the population aged ≥ 10 years in the city of Padangsidimpuan is 14.83 cigarettes (more than one pack). The average number of cigarettes smoked was found in South Tapanuli Regency with as many as 16.40 cigarettes (Health Office of Sumatera Utara, 2017).

The problem of tobacco consumption is not only a problem at the regional level, but it is a global

epidemiological problem. In 2003, the World Health Assembly (World Health Assembly) issued a framework for tobacco control, the Tobacco Control Framework (FCTC). The FCTC is a global effort to protect present and future generations from health, economic, social and environmental impacts caused by cigarette consumption and cigarette smoke exposure. Broadly speaking, the FCTC regulates the control of advertising, promotion and sponsorship of tobacco products, protection for passive smokers, tobacco product packaging and labeling, tobacco taxes and excise and restrictions on the smuggling and illegal sale of tobacco and its products. 193 member states of the United Nations (UN), Indonesia is the only Asian country that has not accessed the FCTC (TCSC-IAKMI, 2015).

In an effort to protect individuals, society and the environment against exposure to cigarette smoke, the Indonesian government has various policies in controlling tobacco, namely establishing a KTR policy to protect the entire community from the dangers of cigarette smoke through Law Number 36 of 2009 concerning Health in article 115 paragraph 1 and 2 which mandate the regional government must determine and implement KTR in their areas, including health care facilities, teaching and learning places, children's playgrounds, places of worship, public transportation, workplaces, public places. Government Regulation (PP) No. 109 of 2012 concerning Safeguarding material containing addictive substances in the form of tobacco products in article 50 states 7 orders are declared as KTR. Joint Regulation Number 188/ MENKES/PB/I/ 2011 and Number 7 of 2011 concerning KTR Implementation Guidelines, Permenkes No. 28 of 2013 concerning the inclusion of health warnings in the form of pictures and writing on tobacco product packaging, various policies have adopted important points in the FCTC (TCSC-IAKMI, 2015).

No-smoking area is a room or area that is declared prohibited from carrying out production activities, sales, advertisements, promotions, and/or use of cigarettes. The reason for the implementation of the KTR is that everyone has the right to protection against the dangers of cigarettes, dangerous tobacco smoke and has no safe limits, designated areas for smoking and the air circulation system is unable to provide effective protection. So that protection is only effective if 100% of a place is free from cigarette smoke (Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia, 2011).

Based on Law No. 36 on Health was passed in 2009, there were 49 regional regulations at the regency/municipality level, 102 regulations of the Regent/Mayor and 13 provinces in Indonesia which have KTR policies. Padangsidimpuan City Government is one of the regions that has KTR regulations, namely regional regulation No.7 in 2012 concerning the implementation of KTR (TCSC-IAKMI, 2015).

The effective implementation of KTR will make a positive contribution to reducing the prevalence of cigarette consumption and exposure to secondhand smoke. Panjaitan, Elisabeth (2015) conducted a study on "Analysis of the Implementation of Medan City Regulation Number 3 of 2014 concerning KTR in Schools in Medan City". Panjaitan, Elisabeth (2015) found a lack of communication from the Regional Government to the school leadership regarding socialization of KTR implementation, lack of resources in terms of facilities and infrastructure for the application of KTR in schools, the lack of response from the target/implementing policy and the lack of running bureaucracy in the application of KTR in schools.

So as a form of implementation of regional regulations on KTR there are regions or regions that have been said to be effective and efficient in implementing these regional regulations, but there are also regions that have not been able to carry out

effectively and efficiently. Some areas in Indonesia, KTR that have been running well, for example, the City of Bandung with regional regulations No.3 in 2005, and the City of Surabaya with regional regulations No.5 in 2008 (TCSC-IAKMI, 2015).

Since the KTR policy in Padangsidimpuan City was put into effect since 2013, the implementation of KTR and the sanction of actions have been officially implemented since the enactment. Every place that has been designated as a KTR must implement the policy. The head of the agency is fully responsible for the implementation of KTR in their respective working areas. The KTR policy in Padangsidimpuan City shows that there has not been a significant change since it was officially promulgated for about five years. Based on the results of a survey on the level of compliance with KTR policy implementation conducted by the Peloporidimpuan Pelopor NGO in 2016, the lowest level of compliance was in public areas by 5%, teaching and learning areas by 7%, public transport by 10%, while the most compliance levels high is a workplace by 26%, a place of worship by 20%, a place for children to play by 18% health care facilities by 14% of the 7 (seven) KTR arrangements. From the survey results where the teaching and learning process is the second lowest place (KTR Compliance Survey Report in Padangsidimpuan City, 2017). The survey results show that the implementation of KTR policies in the teaching and learning process is still low and it needs to be consistently fostered and supervised by the KTR monitoring team in Padangsidimpuan City.

Based on a preliminary survey conducted by researchers in the teaching and learning process in 198 locations from 6 (six) districts in the City of Padangsidimpuan namely elementary school equivalent, junior high school equivalent and high school equivalent and Higher Education. Seeing from all the places of the teaching and learning process in Padangsidimpuan City, no one has yet set

and implemented KTR in their area. The low level of compliance with the implementation of the KTR Padangsidimpuan regional regulation, as there are still many people smoking in KTR (teachers, school guards/security guards, sellers in the canteen, and parents of students), in fact many smokers who still violate the KTR regional regulations, by continuing to smoke in the area included in STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan which is a health-based high school is still often found violations occur on campus. School is one of the KTR, because it will disrupt teaching and learning activities. Some lecturers, education staff and even security guards/campus guards casually smoke on campus without thinking of the consequences of these bad habits, the discovery of cigarette butts around the campus area, the availability of cigarette ashtrays in the lecturers' room and in the canteen, the lack of KTR markings (stickers, placards, banners, billboards, billboards), and the absence of supervision conducted by the manager or person in charge of the area (Chair of STIKES) and no sanctions have been applied to the campus. The effect of that habit is when the students who see it feel that smoking is a natural thing to do. This assumption will more or less influence students to try smoking. Most students in Indonesia have now become active smokers. Some of them openly show that they are smokers and consider it a common thing, can even be regarded as proof that smokers are cool. Some students who smoke do not all dare to show their identities for fear of being punished by lecturers and parents who forbid their children to smoke.

The results of interviews conducted by researchers to the Head of PMK of the Health Office and the Head of Basic Education of the Padangsidimpuan City Education Office, the implementation of KTR policies in Padangsidimpuan City has not been maximally carried out, this can be seen from budget constraints, the absence of APBD allocated by the Padangsidimpuan City Government to support KTR policies.

In addition, cross-sectoral coordination in conducting coaching and supervision also has not gone well. Padangsidimpuan City Health Office as a leading sector has not really realized its duties and obligations to carry out various activities, such as cross-sector and community outreach, training to monitoring and law enforcement teams, coaching and supervision of 7 (seven) areas, and the absence of law enforcement against violations of KTR. Observations made by researchers and the results of a survey conducted by Pelopor NGOs on the low level of KTR compliance, especially in the teaching and learning process, this shows that the regional regulation of Padangsidimpuan City Number 7 of 2012 concerning KTR has not been well implemented by policy makers. Based on the description, the researcher is interested in analyzing the implementation of KTR policy in the place of teaching and learning process in Padangsidimpuan City, especially in STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan.

RESEARCH METHODS

Design of The Study

The study employed was a qualitative study with phenomenology approach. This study was conducted at the STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan, Sumatera Utara Province.

Informants of The Study

Subjects of the study were from at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan in Padangsidimpuan, in which they were the ones who understand the policies and implement the non-smoking area (KTR) policy. Patients were selected by using purposive sampling method with informants in this study were the Chair of STIKES, Chair of Facilities/Infrastructure, Chair of Student Affairs for Lecturers, Employees, Security Guardians, Students, Student Parents and Seller of the Cafeteria.

Data Collection and Analysis

The data were collected by using in-depth interview, direct observation, and

documentation. The data were analyzed by Miles and Huberman model namely through data reduction, presentation, and data verification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determinants of Implementation of Non-Smoking Area (KTR) Policy in STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan

There are four factors that will influence a policy implementation process. The first factor is how communication is interwoven in the policy implementation process. The availability of resources is the next factor. The third factor that influences the success and failure in the policy implementation process is the commitment or attitude of the policy implementer. The last factor is the bureaucratic structure. All of these factors will determine the implementation of the policy in accordance with the objectives or not, as follows:

Communication

Communication is the first important factor in policy implementation. Communication aims to provide information from the authorities to the policy implementer about the intent of the policy implementation. Implementing the regional regulation policy of KTR Padangsidimpuan in this case is an elementary school. Implementers of the KTR Padangsidimpuan regional regulations in the campus environment are the Chair of STIKES, Chair of Facilities/Infrastructure, Lecturers, Employees, Security Guards, Students, and Sellers in the Canteen. The campus has the authority or duty to communicate the policy of the Padangsidimpuan KTR regional regulation in schools to all campus residents as the policy object. Communication must be conveyed clearly and accurately so that it is easy to understand and runs in accordance with the KTR policy objectives within the Higher Education Institution in Padangsidimpuan City.

The Edward III model suggests that policy communication consists of 3 dimensions, namely:

1. Transmission

The transmission dimension expects that the policy is conveyed to the policy objectives so that the objectives of the policy can be understood and implemented properly. Socialization became a communication tool for tertiary institutions in the City to convey KTR policies on campus. The socialization activity was once carried out by the Health Service. This is as explained by Mrs. S as Chairman of STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"Until now we have never received an invitation regarding socialization regarding the regional regulations of Padangsidimpuan City Number 7 of 2012 concerning KTR deck, we also have not received a circular from either the Health Office or the Education Office." (Informant K-1).

Based on the above informant's quote, it can be seen that the informant has not received any information about the written policy regarding Padangsidimpuan City Regulation No. 7/2012 concerning KTR from the Health Service as the initiator.

The results of interviews between researchers and several informants about the socialization activities have been carried out by the school or campus. This is as explained by Mrs. J as Chair of facilities/infrastructure in the STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan environment that:

"The KTR policy socialization was carried out in accordance with the school regulations at the beginning of the school year, not the regional regulation policy of Padangsidimpuan, about the KTR deck. For teachers how to socialize it by conveying to meetings, if you want to smoke there the place ... not in the teacher's room, especially passive smokers will be affected the most from smokers who smoke in any place." (Informant K-2).

The statement was made clear by Mrs. L as a Lecturer in the STIKES

Darmais Padangsidimpuan environment explaining:

"The campus has conducted socialization regarding the policy but it is not a regional regulation policy in Padangsidimpuan about KTR, during the campus meetings and during the new school year attended by parents of students and students. In my opinion, the socialization is not useful because the Foundation provides a place to smoke in the school environment." (Informant U-1).

The same thing was stated by T as a student at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"Yes, there have been, there have been socializations to our parents and we also received new students. The socialization was in the form of guidance and explanation of campus regulations, one of which was the KTR policy on campus, but not the regional regulation policy of the City of Padangsidimpuan about KTR yes ma'am." (Informant U-2).

STIKES School Darmais Padangsidimpuan communicates KTR policy through socialization. The socialization is carried out when there is a new school year. The socialization was conducted by inviting parents and students to the campus to explain about the rules or regulations on campus including KTR on campus. Submission of information about campus rules regarding smoking bans is also done directly to students on a daily basis on campus. Communication between the Chair of STIKES, Chair of facilities/infrastructure Lecturers, students and employees is always reminded not to smoke in the campus area. The socialization was also carried out during the campus meeting. The conclusion from the explanation above is the dimension of transition in the implementation of KTR policy carried out by means of socialization during campus meetings. Socialization is an important communication tool because an information in the policy will be conveyed well to the target and will affect the successful implementation of the policy.

Based on the results of research from Panjaitan (2015) concluded that after KTR

socialization was conducted at three schools in Medan, as many as 59% of respondents who wanted or planned to stop smoking. Continuous, targeted and targeted socialization will not only provide protection to passive smokers but will also reduce the number of active smokers.

2. Clarity

The dimension of clarity in policy communication wants policies to be understood by policy implementers and targets. The clarity that is received by the implementer and the policy objectives is very important in order to know the purpose and purpose of the policy. Some informants claimed that they did not know of the policy but they understood that smoking in schools or colleges was not permitted.

As explained by Mr. DM as parents of students at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"...I don't know if there is a local regulation policy like that in this school, but I know that smoking in schools or colleges is indeed not allowed." (Informant U-3).

The opinion was clarified by Mr. A as an employee at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"...The socialization of the local regulation policy on KTR on campus I think is still unclear because there are still a number of Doses and parents of students who smoke in the school environment as if they did not know if there were such regulations." (Informant U-4).

The results of observations in the field also found a number of smoking items in the campus corridor. In addition, several cigarette butts were thrown carelessly in front of the class corridor. This shows that the lecturer is used to smoking in the campus corridor.

Some of the information above can be concluded that the submission of KTR policy is still unclear. Understanding of the policy, especially for lecturers or employees, security guards, sellers in the canteen, and parents of students and students may be hampered if the Chair of STIKES does not convey the policy to all

people in the campus environment, because the socialization held is aimed at all communities in the the campus environment.

The results of interviews with lecturers and parents about the implementation of the KTR policy at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan showed that some parents claimed they did not know about the policy but they understood that smoking at the school was prohibited. Some lecturers on campus also smoke in the school environment but only in the lecturer room. The results of observations found several lecturers smoking in the campus corridor, even found cigarette butts thrown around the class corridor that indicate that smoking in the campus environment STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan is a common thing to do. This is certainly not in accordance with the regional regulations policy of Padangsidimpuan City on KTR and Permendikbud No. 64 of 2015 which clearly provides a ban on smoking in the school environment. Article 3 of the Permendikbud policy No. 64 of 2015 states that the KTR targets in the school or campus environment are the Principal, lecturers, education staff, students, and other parties such as parents of students in the campus environment.

The conclusion of the above explanation is that the KTR policy socialization at universities in Padangsidimpuan City is still unclear because there are parents of students who claim not to know about the policy and found several lecturers and employees who smoke on campus.

3. Consistency

The Edward III model explains that the consistency dimension wants policy implementation to take place effectively by way of issuing implementation instructions that must be consistent and clear so that the applied policy is not confusing. The dimension of consistency of higher education in Padangsidimpuan City cannot be considered a consistent attitude because the canteen sells cigarettes that are in the

environment and are used specifically for smoking. The place in question is located not far from the classroom. The canteen is a place for students to buy snacks during campus breaks, which gives lecturers and staff space to buy and smoke. This is in accordance with the results of interviews with Mrs. J as Chair of facilities/infrastructure in the STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan environment that:

"...There is a designated smoking area created by the Foundation, because all the lecturers and male employees who teach or work on this campus smoke. The place is intended so that those who smoke do not interfere with those who do not smoke so it is just during recess at the gathering. In the area marsigaret because it is cool and can relax. Then we have not provided a seat under the tree. We drive him out indirectly. Finally, now who smoke a little" (Informant K-2).

Another opinion was delivered by Mr. A Seller in the canteen about the existence of a special smoking area in STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"If I myself do agree there is a special place to make lecturers or, male employees and parents of students do not smoke in any place. If not provided, it will be detrimental to non-smokers too because some of the students' parents smoke in any place." (Informant U-5).

The results of the interview above show that there is no consistency between the policies implemented and the reality in the field. The KTR policy on campus clearly emphasizes that the campus environment is a KTR. Study of documentation on campus rules also shows inconsistent results because on campus rules listed in the aspects of order and safety explains that in the campus environment lecturers, employees and students should not smoke, drink/carry/distribute liquor, drugs or the like.

Data obtained from observations at tertiary institutions in the City of Padangsidimpuan shows the inconsistency

of the campus with the KTR policy because a lecturer was found smoking in front of the classroom. The results of the interview also received recognition from Mr. S as the school guard/campus security guard at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"I often smoke on campus but I smoke when I am not guarding it at the campus gate or at the security post. Usually I smoke in the canteen room during teaching breaks or during breaks." (Informant U-6).

This indicates the consistency of implementing KTR policies at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan is not going well because there are a number of lecturers and employees as implementers instead showing an attitude that is not in line with the policy by smoking in the campus environment. Padangsidimpuan City's regional regulation policy on KTR and Permendikbud Number 64 of 2015 gives no smoking orders in the school environment, rejects offers of advertisements, promotions, sponsorships in any form, then the campus is expected to include smoking-related prohibitions in campus rules. The targets of the policy are the Chair of STIKES, Chair of Facilities/Infrastructure, Chair of Student Affairs for Lecturers, Employees, Security Guardians, Students, Student Parents and Seller of the Cafeteria.

Implementing KTR policies on the STIKES campus Darmais Padangsidimpuan are the Principal, Deputy Chair of STIKES, Chair of Facilities/Infrastructure, Lecturers, Employees. Consistency in implementing policies at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan has not been seen because there is a special place provided by the Chair of STIKES as a smoking area. The smoking area is located not far from the administrative space. The campus made a special smoking area to localize lecturers and parents of students who smoke in any place. The current Chair of STIKES agrees with the existence of the area on the grounds that it is everyone's right, but now the area has begun to be eliminated by not providing a seat under a shady tree in the area.

The conclusion from the above explanation is that the campus has included a smoking ban in the school rules but it is not a regional regulation policy of the City of Padangsidimpuan about KTR and has tried to eliminate the designated smoking area but the Chair of STIKES claimed to agree if there are designated smoking areas in schools.

Resource

Resources become a factor supporting the success of communication carried out by the implementer of the policy to the object of the policy. Resources have a very influential role in the process of implementing a KTR policy on campus that is related to the readiness of the implementing party. Available resources are expected to support the implementation of the policy, if the resources do not support, of course, it will hamper the implementation of the policy. Appropriate support facilities can also maximize the objectives of a policy. Resources in the process of implementing KTR policies on campus relate to the readiness of the implementing party. These resources can be in the form of human resources, budget resources, equipment resources. Following are the results of research on the implementation of KTR regional policy resources in Higher Education in Padangsidimpuan City:

1. Human Resources

Human resources from the campus can be seen from the number of staff who handle the policy, the expertise of the implementing members, relevant information about policy implementation and other preparations. The human resources that are used as implementing the regional regulation policy of Padangsidimpuan City about KTR on campus are the Guardian Lecturers assisted by the Deputy Chair of Student Affairs. Following is the explanation from the Chairman of STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"There is no team specifically dealing with the cigarette problem. But that will later be

included in the violation of the campus code of conduct so that the one handling the program will be his Guardian Lecturer, assisted by the Deputy Head of Student Affairs." (Informant K-1).

This was reinforced by the opinion of Mrs. R as Chair of the Student Affairs Division at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"The coordination of the implementation of handling the policy is largely carried out by the Deputy Chair of Student Affairs and Guardian Lecturers." (Informant K-3).

At present the number of members who handle KTR policies in the STIKES environment Darmais Padangsidimpuan is sufficient but is constrained by several lecturers who also teach at other campuses. This situation hampered campus coordination. The information was obtained during an interview with Mrs. L as Guardian Lecturer in the STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan environment as follows:

"There are also lecturers here who teach in other schools, for policies like that waiting for a forum. Policy matters can be conveyed at the meeting." (Informant U-1).

Readiness of human resources in the implementation of KTR policies at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan uses the Deputy Head of Student Affairs because violations committed are included in the campus code of conduct namely pollution of the campus environment. Deputy Lecturer Guardian is assisted by Deputy Chair of Student Affairs to oversee the implementation of the policy, but currently the existing human resources cannot be maximized.

2. Budget Resources

Budget resources in the implementation of KTR policies in Higher Education in Padangsidimpuan City are sufficient because the campus program does not require large funding. Funding for the program is only in the installation of no-smoking signs. Installation of no-smoking signs using the campus equipment budget. This was conveyed by Mrs. S as Chair of STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"For the program budget, the campus does not budget specifically because the program does not require a lot of costs. Writing posts forbidden to smoke only uses other funds included in class equipment." (Informant K-1).

Budget resources used for the implementation of KTR policies are not specifically budgeted by the campus. The campus does not budget specifically because there is no specific program to respond to the policy. This was reinforced by the opinions of Mrs. R as Deputy Chair of the Student Affairs as follows:

"We made the budget with socialization and meetings. For the installation of pictures, it is forbidden to use class equipment money." (Informant K-3).

The socialization was the initial step for the campus to respond to the policy, but the socialization carried out included the introduction of schools or the beginning of the new school year so that the budget was included in the socialization at the beginning of the new school year. The socialization was also carried out during the lecturer meeting with the Chair of STIKES. The campus put up a no-smoking sign in each class. The installation of the sign uses the campus management component budget, including class equipment. The Chair of STIKES wants to make STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan free from exposure to cigarette smoke.

The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research conducted by Taruna (2016) which states that Gadjah Mada High School Yogyakarta has carried out the application stage by implementing the KTR Policy in the form of budgeting and equipment by conducting socialization and having installed no-smoking signs. Resource and disposition factors are supporting factors that can be found in the Implementation of KTR Policy in Gadjah Mada High School Yogyakarta.

3. Equipment Resources

Equipment resources are important in policy implementation. Equipment resources are used to support policy

implementation. The implementation of the regional regulation policy of Padangsidimpuan City regarding KTR also requires equipment to support the success of the policy objectives. The equipment resources used to implement the KTR policy at the University in Padangsidimpuan City only use the no-smoking sign and for the rest using available human resources namely the Lecturer Guardian assisted by the Deputy Chair of the Student Affairs Supervised by the Chair of STIKES.

There is no special equipment from the campus because there is no specific program to handle the policy. Observation results at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan were not found as a no-smoking sign, but according to informants at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan the sign did exist but was not a banner of Padangsidimpuan City's regional regulation policy on KTR but Permendikbud No. 64 of 2015 which clearly gave a smoking ban had been removed by the security guard. Following is the explanation from Mr. S as the school guard/security guard at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"Putting up no-smoking posts in the front near the campus gate has a deck, but that also has no effect on us who smoke and have been removed a few months ago." (Informant U-6).

The Padangsidimpuan City regional regulation policy on KTR gives an order to the campus to put the KTR mark in the campus environment. The results of observations at the City of Padangsidimpuan College did not find any sign of no smoking. The no-smoking sign was supposed to be in every college in Padangsidimpuan City but it was not found and according to some lecturers the sign did not exist. There are also no regulations in which there are smoking bans in Padangsidimpuan City College.

Edwards III (1980) states that important resources in supporting the implementation of government policies include HR, budget and facilities and infrastructure. The results of this study are

consistent with the results of research conducted by Tarigan (2014) in schools in Medan which stated that there was still a lack of communication from the Regional Government to the school leadership in terms of KTR socialization, there was still a lack of resources in terms of facilities and infrastructure for the application of KTR in schools, there is still a lack of response from the target/implementing policy and the bureaucracy is still lacking in the implementation of KTR in schools.

Based on the results of the study, it can be seen that the implementation of the policy will run optimally if it is supported by human resources, budget availability, equipment resources, and adequate authority resources. If one does not meet expectations, it will become an obstacle in the implementation of the No Smoking Area policy.

Disposition or Attitude

Disposition or attitude is a characteristic of implementing the policy. This relates to how the characteristics of implementers who support or reject the policy. Implementers are expected to have the capacity to implement policies. Implementing policies selected in accordance with their capacities must have a strong commitment to implementing the policies. The attitude or commitment of the policy implementers is needed in the implementation of the policy. A strong commitment from the implementer of the policy can succeed the implementation of the policy, for that the demands of commitment to the implementer of the policy must be strong and full dedication to the implementation of a policy.

KTR policy implementers on campus include the Chair of STIKES, Deputy Chair of Student Affairs, and Lecturer Guardians. The parties involved in implementing KTR policies on campus are expected to have the dedication to carry out these responsibilities. The Chair of STIKES has the responsibility to oversee and succeed the policy by working with all

lecturers and staff. The campus made an effort to socialize the KTR policy on campus to the target group, installing no-smoking signs in the campus area. The attitude of the policy implementers in the Padangsidimpuan City college still has not shown full support for the KTR policy implementation in the tertiary institution, this is evidenced by the results of an interview with Mrs. R as Deputy Chair of Student Affairs at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"...if you are going to apply the regional regulation policy of Padangsidimpuan City about KTR, it can't yet be maximal and doesn't seem effective because the Chair of STIKES actually applies a smoking-free policy in schools located near the lecturer room which has shady trees which according to lecturers and parents of cool students to hang out." (Informant K-3).

Field observations also found lecturers who were smoking on campus. The lecturer smoked in front of the classroom which was included in the school environment. This shows the attitude that is not in line with the KTR policy in the campus environment.

The opinions of the implementers of the policies on the implementation of KTR policies at the University of Padangsidimpuan City vary. Some lecturers agreed with the policy, but there were also those who did not agree to see the condition of the lecturers at Padangsidimpuan City College. Following are the opinions of Mrs. R as Deputy Chair of the Student Affairs Section at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"If I do not agree to the deck if there is a designated smoking area on campus, but what else can I do to see the condition of teachers and parents of students who indeed cannot be regulated anymore to not smoke on campus ..." (Informant K-3).

Another response was conveyed by Mrs. L as the guardian lecturer at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"If I myself do agree there is a special place to make lecturers or parents of students not

smoke in any place. If it is not provided, it will be detrimental to non-smokers as well because some of the lecturers smoke everywhere. In my own opinion, as long as certain areas are still a lot of plants, there is no problem. But if for areas where there are no plants but there is cigarette smoke, such areas are obliged to make areas without cigarettes. Can not forbid people to stop smoking, there are thousands of people who live from cigarettes, sorry if forbidden, those who live from cigarettes. Just as a smoker, you must be able to put yourself in order not to disturb others." (Informant U-1).

Mr. S as the School Guard/Security Guard at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan gave a response regarding the existence of a designated smoking area as follows:

"In my opinion a special place for smoking is necessary because for a smoker if he doesn't smoke it tastes bitter. A designated smoking area in this school is needed because there are some lecturers who smoke including me, but what I don't like is that many teachers and parents of students smoke in this school. Their smoking habit is obtained when at home brought to school when mengatar or pick up their children at school. Actually, a special place for smoking on this campus is to provide a place for smokers not to smoke in any place, but from the public many people get bad responses." (Informant U-6).

The observations found a location that was used by the campus as a special place for smoking or the canteen. The location is not far from the lecturer hall. The implementation of KTR policy at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan which can be seen during interviews and observations shows that the attitude or disposition of policy implementers still cannot fully support the implementation of KTR policies in schools. STIKES Chair's policy is to create a special place for smoking in the campus area. The Deputy Head of Student Affairs gave an opinion that disagreed with the policy, but could not do much because the condition of the lecturers who already

had smoking habits that were difficult to regulate. The situation of such lecturers is also complicated by the opinion of the Chair of STIKES who agrees if there is a special smoking area despite efforts to eliminate the place. The area is located near the lecturer hall and canteen with shady trees suitable for relaxing while smoking.

The Chair of STIKES made the designated smoking area be eliminated by the first step of cutting down trees. The elimination of the designated smoking area makes lecturers and parents of students who smoke less control. Some of the lecturers and parents of students smoke along the campus corridor, and some even smoke in front of the class, in addition there are also lecturers who smoke in the lecturer room.

This is in line with the results of Nasyrudin's research (2013) which states that non-compliance of teachers, employees, security guards and sellers in Katin and visitors (parents of students) due to the absence of initiatives and sanctions in force, so it cannot cause a deterrent effect on violators of the rules making this KTR policy implementation not going well.

Based on the results of the study, it can be seen that there is no full commitment and compliance with the implementation of the implementation of regional regulation policy No. 7 of 2012 concerning KTR in Padangsidimpuan City and monitoring of any violations that occur in the KTR as well as strict sanctions are imposed on implementing the policy regarding KTR policy in the place of the learning process.

Bureaucratic Structure

Bureaucratic structure is a factor that needs to be considered besides communication, resources, and disposition. Bureaucratic structure has an influence in the implementation of policies. Implementation of the policy will involve many people in it. Some parties involved in implementing the policy will work together to form a bureaucratic structure to realize the implementation of policies in accordance with the objectives.

Bureaucratic structure has a leader who has a role as a person in charge. The leader of the bureaucratic structure in implementing the Padangsidimpuan City policy on KTR in Higher Education in the City of Padangsidimpuan is the Chair of STIKES.

A policy implementation certainly has a standard operating procedure (SOP). SOP is used as a guide by implementing the policy in carrying out its duties. The implementation of the KTR regional regulation policy at the University of Padangsidimpuan City is not entirely the same as the SOP, it is only done simply as explained by Mrs. S as the Chair of STIKES at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan:

"For this SOP, KTR policy may not have been implemented as it should, but the campus has included a ban on smoking in schools in the order. Implementation of the code of conduct is supervised by the Chair of STIKES assisted by lecturers and employees. The campus has also put up no-smoking signs in the form of banners. There are no guidelines from schools to implement KTR policies, only to localize smokers so as not to disturb non-smokers. The Chair of STIKES provides a special place for smoking or canteen in the campus environment, there are shade trees so the smoke can be neutralized. So that place is made a special area for smoking. But for now the campus is trying to eliminate the KTR." (Informant K-1).

The implementation of the policy has a team consisting of guardian lecturers assisted by Deputy Head of Student Affairs and overseen by the Chair of STIKES. The task of the team was explained by Mrs. S as the Chair of STIKES at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan as follows:

"The task of the team to succeed the program is only to supervise lecturers or parents of students on campus, if there are violators will be given sanctions. Guardian lecturers also post banned smoking in the classroom." (Informant K-1).

To carry out this policy, coordination is needed. Following is an explanation from Mrs. R as Deputy Chair of Student Affairs

at STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan regarding coordination of KTR policy implementation:

"...to respond to the KTR policy in the campus environment there is coordination between the Chair of STIKES, the deputy head of the student affairs division and the trustee lecturer." (Informant K-3).

This is reinforced by the opinion of Mrs. L as the guardian lecturer at Darmais Padangsidimpuan STIKES:

"Coordination to respond to the policy is carried out by the guardian lecturer with the vice chair of student affairs overseen by the Chair of STIKES." (Informant U-1)

The coordination carried out by the campus in implementing the KTR policy is only based on the campus rules and regulations involving the Homeroom Lecturer and Deputy Chair of Student Affairs and overseen by the Chair of STIKES. Coordination between members is adjusted to their respective tasks.

The bureaucratic structure in the implementation of the KTR regional regulation policy in the University of Padangsidimpuan City has not been made in the form of detailed SOP guidelines to regulate the division of tasks implementing the policy so that the policy implementation has no structure and runs less effectively. The campus has implemented an order to include a smoking ban in the school environment in the campus rules, in addition to that the campus has also put a no-smoking sign on campus similar to the Permendikbud banner No. 64 of 2015 in accordance with the rules set by the STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan. KTR policies in universities are considered not too complicated so that the policy implementers carry out tasks according to their position on campus. The KTR policy implementation team in Higher Education in Padangsidimpuan City consists of the Chair of STIKES, Deputy Chair of Student Affairs. The Chair of STIKES is assisted by the deputy headmaster who is assigned as a leader, innovator, motivator, and oversees the ongoing activities on campus. Guardian

lecturers and other lecturers are responsible to the Chair of STIKES to carry out teaching and learning activities effectively and efficiently and give directions to parents of students not to smoke in the campus environment, if there are still violators will be given sanctions. Employees help smooth the implementation of policies in the administration of higher education.

The division of tasks that are not too complicated in the implementation of KTR policy at the University of Padangsidimpuan City is apparently still not maximized. The coordination of the implementation of the policy starts with the Guardian Lecturer, assisted by the Deputy Chair of Student Affairs. The implementation of the policy is overseen by the Chair of STIKES. There are still many violations that occur on the campus. Based on the description above it can be concluded that there has not been an effort from the school that is able to overcome the problems associated with the implementation of the regional regulation policy of Padangsidimpuan on KTR in tertiary institutions.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Panjaitan (2015) which states that the lack of effective monitoring and evaluation of supervision results by officers results in the community becoming accustomed to smoking in the school environment. That is because the officers and employees included in the anti-smoking task force team or even visitors are very careless in conducting surveillance and are influenced by the wider environment, making it difficult to reach the corners where smokers are fleeing to find safe avoid from hospital staff.

The above statement is also supported by the results of research from Youth (2016) which says that KTR will not run optimally if a KTR enforcement task force has not yet been formed, where one of its tasks is to carry out supervision of the KTR.

Monitoring and supervision of the implementation of KTR policy has not been conducted by the Padangsidimpuan City

Health Office because the monitoring team's decree has not been received from the Padangsidimpuan City Government.

Based on the results of this research, it can be seen that although there is no committee or monitoring team for the implementation of KTR policy, this should not be the reason that a policy has not been implemented optimally. The school can combine the supervision team with the bureaucratic structure section in the university, no need to create a separate unit. This will make it easier for the campus to implement the policy and do not need to spend additional funds as expressed by the Chairman of STIKES Darmais Padangsidimpuan.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

The KTR policy in Padangsidimpuan City was officially put into effect on July 22, 2013 and the implementation of KTR and sanctions have been officially implemented since the enactment. Every place that has been designated as a KTR must implement the policy including the place of the teaching and learning process. The head of the agency is fully responsible for the implementation of KTR in their respective working areas. The implementation of the regional regulation policy on KTR in Padangsidimpuan City shows that there has not been a significant change since it was officially promulgated for about five years.

Based on the results of research in the field shows that the policy has not been implemented due to the ignorance of the implementor regarding the regional regulation policy on KTR in the City of Padangsidimpuan University, this shows that the level of compliance with the implementation and application of the KTR policy in the teaching and learning process is still not implemented and applied in Padangsidimpuan City College, with reasons:

1. In the communication aspect, there is no tiered and comprehensive socialization from

the local government to all levels of society, especially the basic campus of the same level about the development of KTR policies in the campus environment and knowing the dangers of smoking.

2. In the aspect of resources, the lack of equipment supply, and the availability of funds to support the KTR policy.

3. In the aspect of disposition, there is no full commitment and implementor compliance with policy implementation and there is no strict sanctions against violators of KTR policies

4. In the aspect of bureaucratic structure, there is no monitoring team to implement the KTR policy implementation.

SUGGESTION

1. To the local government in Padangsidimpuan City to carry out intensive and sustainable health promotion in the form of socialization through audiovisual media that contains information about KTR policies that should be carried out in the teaching and learning environment; Formation of the KTR policy committee or supervisory team; Establishment of APBD of Padangsidimpuan City as the implementation of KTR regional regulation policy, providing facilities and infrastructure in the implementation of KTR policy; Increase work commitments to the implementation of KTR policies and enforce strict sanctions for violations of KTR policies in the teaching and learning environment.

2. To the campus to take a persuasive approach from the college to campus residents and parents of students who smoke about the smoking ban, so that the school environment is free of cigarette smoke to be an example for students.

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